

Prognosticating Crystallization Kinetics in Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients

Pravin Kumar Singh*, Ashutosh Tiwari

Institute of Advanced Materials, IAAM, Gammalkilsvägen 18, Ulrika 590 53, Sweden

*E-mail: pravin.singh@iaam.se

Presenting Author' Biography

Dr. Pravin Kumar Singh is an MSCA Post Doctoral Fellow at Institute of Advanced Materials, IAAM, Sweden. Before this fellowship, he served as a Group Leader at VBRI Innovation Centre, New Delhi, India. He was an assistant professor in physics at KIPM College of Engineering and Technology in Gorakhpur, India. Before that, he worked as a Guest Faculty in Madan Mohan Malaviya University of Technology, Gorakhpur, India for two years. Dr. Singh has a PhD in physics and two master's degrees, M.Sc. in electronics and communication and M.Tech in optoelectronics and laser technology. As per his research contributions, he has written a book and more than 50 papers that have been published in well-known international journals. He is Managing Editor of Advanced Materials Proceedings and reviewers in many high impacts reputed journals.

Graphical Abstract

Abstract

A major challenge in drug development is the low aqueous solubility or membrane permeability of the active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs). Almost 80 % of drugs under investigation exhibit poor water solubility and additional efforts are required to improve this feature. The development of amorphous drugs is considered the most effective way to improve the bioavailability of the APIs. The non-crystalline nature of active substances enhancing many important physico-chemical properties represents at the same time a major disadvantage of fragile stability. In this talk, an overview of amorphous APIs, highlighting their specific solid-state properties and the benefits they provide to the pharmaceutical industry, is provided. Nucleation, crystal growth, and the impact of environment on crystallization rate and size is discussed in detail. Moreover, kinetics of crystallization for amorphous APIs with an emphasis on recent advances in predictive modelling and computer simulations is given. With these modelling techniques, novel medication formulations with enhanced stability and therapeutic performance have been discussed.

Keywords: Drug development, Crystallization kinetics, Active pharmaceutical ingredients, Bioavailability, Solubility

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